

A HORIZONTAL MINING FOR SPECIFIC USERS IN SOCIAL NETWORKS WITH APRIORI BASED ALGORITHM

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Abstract:

Sequences are commonly occurring in any metric space that facilitates either total or partial ordering. Events in time, codons or nucleotides in an amino acid, website traversal, computer networks and characters in a text string are examples of where the existence of sequences may be significant and where the detection of frequent (totally or partially ordered) subsequences might be useful. Sequential pattern mining has arisen as a technology to discover such subsequences. An important limitation of algorithms for mining sequential rules common to multiple sequences is that rules are very specific and therefore many similar rules may represent the same situation. To address these issues, we explore the idea of mining "partially-ordered sequential rules" (POSR), a more general form of sequential rules such that items in the antecedent and the consequent of each rule are unordered. We propose the Apriori algorithm for an inherent problem facing all forms of pattern mining algorithm with either constraints or approximate patterns being commonly used solutions. The PSP algorithm was inspired by GSP, but has improvements that make it possible to perform retrieval optimizations. The difference lies in the way that the candidate sequences are organized. GSP and its predecessors use hash tables at each internal node of the candidate tree, whereas the PSP approach organizes the candidates in a prefix-tree according to their common elements which results in lower memory overhead and faster retrievals.

Key Words: Apriori, Partially-Ordered, Sequential Mining & Frequent Itemsets

Introduction:

Sequential pattern mining is an important data mining task with wide applications. It consists of discovering sub sequences that are common to multiple sequences. Several algorithms have been proposed for this task such as GSP, Prefix Span, SPADE and CM-SPADE. However, sequential patterns found by these algorithms are often misleading for the user. The reason is that patterns are found solely on the basis of their support (the percentage of sequences in which they occur). For instance, consider the sequential pattern {Vivaldi}, {Handel}, {Berlioz} meaning that customer(s) bought the music of Vivaldi, Handel and Berlioz in that order. This sequential pattern is said to have a support of 50 %.

A solution to this problem would be to add a measure of the confidence or probability that a pattern will be followed. But adding this information to sequential patterns is not straightforward because they can contain multiple items and sequential pattern mining algorithms have just not been designed for that. An alternative that considers the confidence of a sequential pattern is sequential rule mining.

A sequential rule (also called episode rule, temporal rule or prediction rule) indicates that if some event(s) occur, some other event(s) are likely to follow with a given confidence or probability. Sequential rule mining has been applied in several domains such as drought management stock market analysis weather observation reverse engineering elearning and e-commerce. Algorithms for sequential rule mining are designed to either discover rules appearing in a single sequence across sequences or common to multiple sequences. Association rule mining also has been applied to the learning of sequential patterns mining, which is a restrictive form of association rule mining in the sense that not only the occurrences themselves, but also the order between the occurrences of the items is taken into account. The extraction of sequential patterns has been used in elearning for evaluating the learners' activities and can be used in adapting and customizing resource delivery [7]; discovering and comparison with expected behavioral patterns specified by the instructor that describes an ideal learning path [8]; giving an indication of how to best organize the educational web space and be able to make suggestions to learners who share similar characteristics [9]; generating personalized activities to different groups of learners [10]; supporting the evaluation and validation of learning site designs [11]; identifying interaction sequences indicative of problems and patterns that are markers of success [12].

The Apriori Algorithm is an influential algorithm for mining frequent item sets for boolean association rules.

- ✓ Consider a database, D, consisting of 9 transactions.
- ✓ Suppose min. support count required is 2 (i.e. $\text{min_sup} = 2/9 = 22\%$)
- ✓ Let minimum confidence required is 70%.
- ✓ We have to first find out the frequent item set using Apriori algorithm.
- ✓ Then, Association rules will be generated using min. support & min. confidence.

Related Work:

In the association rule mining area, most of the research efforts went in the first place to improving the algorithmic performance [29], and in the second place into reducing the output set by allowing the possibility to express constraints on the desired results. Over the past decade a variety of algorithms that address these issues through the refinement of search strategies, pruning techniques and data structures have been developed. While most algorithms focus on the explicit discovery of all rules that satisfy minimal support and confidence constraints for a given dataset, increasing consideration is being given to specialized algorithms that attempt to improve processing time or facilitate user interpretation by reducing the result set size and by incorporating domain knowledge [30]. There are also other specific problems related to the application of association rule mining from e-learning data. When trying to solve these problems, one should consider the purpose of the association models and the data they come from. Nowadays, normally, data mining tools are designed more for power and flexibility than for simplicity. Most of the current data mining tools are too complex for educators to use and their features go well beyond the scope of what an educator might require. As a result, the courses administrator is more likely to apply data mining techniques in order to produce reports for instructors who then use these reports to make decisions about how to improve the student’s learning and the online courses. However, it is most desirable that teachers participate directly in the iterative mining process in order to obtain more valuable rules. But normally, teachers only use the feedback provided by the obtained rules to make decisions about modification to improve the course, detect activities or students with problems, etc. Some of the main drawbacks of association rule algorithms in e-learning are: the used algorithms have too many parameters for somebody non expert in data mining and the obtained rules are far too many, most of them non-interesting and with low comprehensibility. In the following subsections, we will tackle these problems. The application of traditional association algorithms will be simple and efficient. However, association rule mining algorithms normally discover a huge quantity of rules and do not guarantee that all the rules found are relevant. Support and confidence factors can be used for obtaining interesting rules which have values for these factors greater than a threshold value. Although these two parameters allow the pruning of many associations, another common constraint is to indicate the attributes that must or cannot be present in the antecedent or consequent of the discovered rules. Another solution is to evaluate, and post-prune the obtained rules in order to find the most interesting rules for a specific problem. Traditionally, the use of objective interestingness measures has been suggested [39], such as support and confidence, mentioned previously, as well as others measures such as Laplace, chi-square statistic, correlation coefficient, entropy gain, gini, interest, conviction, etc. These measures can be used for ranking the obtained rules in order than the user can select the rules with highest values in the measures that he/she is more interested.

Apriori Algorithm:

Itemset	Sup. Count
{I1, I2}	4
{I1, I3}	4
{I1, I4}	1
{I1, I5}	2
{I2, I3}	4
{I2, I4}	2
{I2, I5}	2
{I3, I4}	0
{I3, I5}	1
{I4, I5}	0

In Classical Apriori algorithm, when candidate item sets are generated, the algorithm needs to test their occurrence frequencies. The manipulation with redundancy will result in high frequency in querying, so tremendous amount of resources will be expended in time or in space. Therefore the improved algorithm was proposed for mining the association rules in generating frequent k item sets. Instead of judging whether these

candidates are frequent item sets after generating new candidates, this new algorithm finds frequent item sets directly and removes the subset that is not frequent, based on the classical Apriori algorithm. The improvement is for reducing query frequencies and storage resources. The improved Apriori algorithm mines frequent item sets without new candidate generation.[6].

Association rule mining also has been applied to the learning of sequential patterns mining, which is a restrictive form of association rule mining in the sense that not only the occurrences themselves, but also the order between the occurrences of the items is taken into account. The extraction of sequential patterns has been used in e-learning for evaluating the learners' activities and can be used in adapting and customizing resource delivery [14]; discovering and comparison with expected behavioral patterns specified by the instructor that describes an ideal learning path [15]; giving an indication of how to best organize the educational web space and be able to make suggestions to learners who share similar characteristics [16]; generating personalized activities to different groups of learners [17]; supporting the evaluation and validation of learning site designs [18]; identifying interaction sequences indicative of problems and patterns that are markers of success [19]. Finally, association rule mining has been used in the e-learning for classification [20]. From a syntactic point of view, the main difference to general association rules is that classification rules have a single condition in the consequent which is the class identifier name. They have been applied in learning material organization [21], student learning assessments [22, 23, 24], course adaptation to the students' behavior [25, 26] and evaluation of educational web sites [27]. This paper is organized in the following way: Section 2 describes the KDD process for association rule mining in e-learning. Section 3 describes the main drawbacks and solutions of applying association rule algorithms in LMS. Finally, in section 4, the conclusions and further research are outlined.

Pseudo Code:

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 $C_k$ : Candidate itemset of size k
 $L_k$ : frequent itemset of size k

 $L_1 = \{\text{frequent items}\};$ 
for ( $k = 1; L_k \neq \emptyset; k++$ ) do begin
     $C_{k+1}$  = candidates generated from  $L_k$ ;
    for each transaction  $t$  in database do
        increment the count of all candidates in  $C_{k+1}$ 
        that are contained in  $t$ 
     $L_{k+1}$  = candidates in  $C_{k+1}$  with min_support
    end
return  $\cup_k L_k$ ;
    
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References:

1. R. Agrawal, T. Imielinski and A. Swami, "Mining Association Rules Between Sets of Items in Large Databases," Proc. 13th ACM SIGMOD Intern. Conf. on Management of Data, pp. 207-216, 1993.
2. D. W. Cheung, J. Han, V. Ng. and Y. Wong, "Maintenance of discovered association rules in large databases: An incremental updating technique," Proc. 12th Intern. Conf. on Data Eng., pp. 106-114, 1996.
3. G. Das, K.-I. Lin, H. Mannila, G. Renganathan and P. Smyth, "Rule Discovery from Time Series," Proc. 4th ACM Intern. Conf. Know. Discovery and Data Mining, pp. 16-22, 1998.
4. U. Faghihi, P. Fournier-Viger and R. Nkambou, "A Computational Model for Causal Learning in Cognitive Agents," Knowledge Based Systems, vol. 30, pp. 48-56, 2012.
5. P. Fournier-Viger, U. Faghihi, R. Nkambou and E. Mephu Nguifo, "CMRules: An Efficient Algorithm for Mining Sequential Rules Common to Several Sequences," Knowledge Based Systems, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 63-76, 2012.
6. Aarti Patil, Seem Kolkur, Deepali Patil: Advanced Apriori Algorithmss," International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research, Volume 4, Issue 8, August-2013.

7. Zaïane, O., Luo, J.: Web usage mining for a better web-based learning environment. In: Proc. of Int. Conf. on advanced technology for education (2001) 60–64.
8. Pahl, C., Donnellan, C.: Data mining technology for the evaluation of web-based teaching and learning systems. In: Proc. of Int. Conf. E-learning (2003) 1-7.
9. Ha, S., Bae, S., Park, S.: Web Mining for Distance Education. In: IEEE Int. Conf. on Management of Innovation and Technology (2000) 715–719.
10. Wang, W., Weng, J., Su, J., Tseng, S.: Learning portfolio analysis and mining in scorm compliant environment. In: ASEE/IEEE Frontiers in Education Conf. (2004) 17–24.
11. Machado, L., Becker, K.: Distance Education: A Web Usage Mining Case Study for the Evaluation of Learning Sites. In: Proc. of Int. Conf. on Advanced Learning Technologies (2003) 360-361.
12. Kay, J., Maisonneuve, N., Yacef, K., Zaiane, O.R. : Mining Patterns of Events in Students' Teamwork Data. In: Proc. of Educational Data Mining Workshop (2006) 1-8